

Care and Management of Dairy animals during the Rainy Season

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Introduction

In India, livestock is an integral part of agriculture and has contributed to the economy since old age. Many farmers in India rear Cattle, Buffaloes, Sheep, Goats, Pigs, Horses, etc. Livestock rearing requires the utmost care and protection of animals from extremes of weather conditions. The rainy season can significantly change the environment, affecting livestock's health and behavior. Excessive moisture and humidity can create a favorable breeding ground for parasites like ticks and worms, leading to health issues like gastrointestinal infections. This monsoon also favors the propagation of pathogenic organisms like bacteria, viruses, fungi, and parasites. Additionally, muddy and waterlogged conditions can cause foot problems in livestock, resulting in lameness and reduced mobility.

Problems of livestock rearing during the rainy season:

The problems encountered by the farmers in the rainy season can be categorized in the following points:

1. Leaky roofs of animal shed

- The leakage of water into animal sheds causes the discomfort of animals. The amount of humidity increases significantly in the shed and thus causes the accumulation of ammonia gas in the shed. That leads to the irritation of the eyes. Wet shed also favors the growth of

many commensal and facultative bacteria.

- Providing adequate shelter for livestock during the rainy season is essential to protect them from the elements. Ensure that the barns or shelters are well-ventilated and free from leaks to prevent moisture buildup and harmful fungi growth. Proper drainage systems around the shelters can help avoid water logging. Bedding material should be kept dry and changed regularly to maintain the comfort and hygiene of the animals (Beyene *et al.*, 2011)

2. Feed and water

- The rainy season doesn't imply a sufficient quantity of safe drinking water for the livestock. Similarly, fodder (Lush green pastures) grows during the rainy season and contains lots of the moisture that fills up the stomach and practically it has no use moreover it leads to animals having digestive problems and watering feces. That's why they should be given dry fodder along with green fodder. Dry fodder and storage feed get wet because of leakage of rainwater from a broken roof, and then it will develop molds. If we give moldy feed to the animals then it can cause aflatoxicosis to them so we should store it properly. Supplementing the animal's diet with

mineral blocks, protein-rich feed, and vitamins is necessary to meet their nutritional requirements (Das and Tripathi, 2008)

- Drinking water should be clean because there is a high possibility of animals falling ill in this season and an adequate water supply is also essential to prevent dehydration, especially during heavy rainfall.

3. Internal parasitic, and bacterial infection

- In the rainy season due to overflow of drain water, the cases of parasitic infestation become high. Farm animals accidentally consume parasitic eggs (eg. Tinea eggs) along with green fodder, which leads to the formation of tissue cysts in the muscles of cattle and pigs.
- Due to the moisture in the rainy season, bacteria spread rapidly. That's why spraying of anthelmintic medicine should be done in this season at the place of keeping animals. This will not affect the bacteria in animals. Regular deworming and vaccinations are vital to protect livestock from gastrointestinal parasites and other common diseases (Meena *et al.*, 2008).

4. External parasitic infestation

- Tick infestation is more frequently observed in the rainy season. A large number of ticks in the animal shed cause haemo protozoan diseases namely trypanosomiasis, theileriosis (East Coast fever), babesiosis, anaplasmosis, and

some rickettsial diseases such as Q fever. East Coast fever is very dangerous, and can even kill animals. To prevent this disease in the rainy season, there must be no flies around the animals (Sharma *et al.*, 2006).

- Ectoparasites like flies cause transmission of the virus causing ephemeral fever in cattle. Before monsoon, cattle require vaccination against hemorrhagic septicemia. Hemorrhagic septicemia is due to Pasteurella infection, which will become dormant during the early monsoon period. Vaccination against foot and mouth disease has to be done during the early monsoon period.

5. Udder infection

- Cases of udder infection are more in the rainy season due to wet sheds and bedding. Unhygienic conditions and waterlogging will cause the flare-up of organisms causing mastitis. The Udder and teats of animals come in contact with the dirty surface and bacteria enter through the teat canal and cause swelling of the teats and udder. If animals are left untreated then it causes the fibrosis of udder and makes them unuseful. Mastitis will affect milk production and cause huge economic losses to the dairy industry. At the national level it causes an annual loss of 12,000 crores (Tomar and Thakur, 2002).

Management of dairy farming in the the rainy season

Some preventive measures must be taken during the rainy season:

1. Before and during the onset of the rainy season animals should be dewormed against various internal parasites.
2. Farm animals should be vaccinated for infectious diseases i.e. Hemorrhagic septicemia, Black quarter, and Foot and Mouth disease.
3. Provide clean and wholesome water for drinking to the animals and provide dry fodder along with green fodder to increase milk yield. Never leave animals for grazing during the rainy season.
4. During the rainy season, there are chances of indigestion, acidosis, and consequent reduction in milk production among milch cattle. "Farmers need to follow scientific feeding and management practices to maintain milk production. While giving green fodder in plenty during the rainy season, to reduce the chances of diarrhea, it can be mixed with straw or can be allowed to dry in sunlight for 2-3 hours. Chances of aflatoxicosis can be reduced by avoiding moist feeds or oil cakes, which are the potential sources of fungal toxins."
5. To prevent the scarcity of fodder, farmers can prepare unconventional

feed like hay and silage. Along with these, they can also use mineral blocks like urea molasses mineral blocks (UMMB) to fulfill the mineral requirements of animals.

6. During the rainy season, farmers need to follow clean milk production practices including cleaning and disinfecting cattle sheds, scientifically constructing dung pits, and following scientific milking practices.
7. Animal sheds should be repaired pre-monsoon to avoid any leakage of water during rain.
8. Provide proper ventilation in the animal house.
9. To prevent zoonotic diseases, slaughterhouses need to follow scientific slaughtering practices including anti-mortem and post-mortem examination of meat. During the rainy season, excess milk production can be utilized for making value-added products. Adequate measures must be taken to control laminitis and foot rot during the rainy season.
10. Proper disposal of the carcass by burning and deep burial method to prevent further spread of the infection.
11. A regular spray of insecticides in the animal shed to control the external parasites.
12. Clean cow dung, overfeed and urine very frequently to prevent animals from udder infections.
13. Avoid long-term stress such as transport and under-nutrition conditions.

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